

IMPACT AND FAILURE ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE PLATES

BY MULTISCALE MODELING

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SUMMARY

An investigation was performed to study the impact damage of the laminated composite plates caused by a low-velocity foreign object with multi-scale modeling based on the concepts of Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS)[3]. In the micro-scale part, we discretize the composite plates through separate modeling of fiber and matrix for the local microscopic analysis. A micro-scale model was developed for predicting the initiation of the damage and the extent of the final damage as a function of material properties, laminate configuration and the impactor's mass, etc. And a macro-scale model was developed for description of global dynamic behavior. The connection between microscopic and macroscopic is implemented by the tied interface constraints of LS-DYNA contact card. A transient dynamic finite element analysis was adopted for calculating the contact force history and the stresses and strains inside the composites during impact resulting from a point-nose impactor. The low-velocity impact events such as contact force, deformation, etc. are simulated in the macroscopic sense and the impact damages, fiber-breakage, matrix cracking and delamination etc. are examined in the microscopic sense.

KEYWORD composite, low-velocity impact, DNS, multiscale modeling

INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced composite materials have been increasingly used in load bearing structures since they have a number of advantages over more conventional materials: high specific strength and stiffness, good fatigue performance and corrosion resistance. A serious obstacle to more widespread use is the sensitivity of composite laminates to impact and static loads in the thickness direction [1]. The energy absorbed during impact is mainly dissipated by a combination of matrix damage, fiber fracture and fiber-matrix debonding and this may lead to significant reductions in the load carrying capability of the laminate. While in ballistic impacts the damage is much localized and clearly visible by external inspection, low velocity impacts involve long contact time between impactor and target, and so produce global structure deformation with internal damage at points far from the contact region.[2]

In this paper, a DNS model is presented for predicting dynamic behavior and damage description of a thin composite laminate subjected to low velocity impact, providing detailed information on the relationship between the impact load and the signals generated by the load. When predicting the response of composite plates until fracture, many scales must be taken into account in order to describe the main deterioration phenomena which control the strength of the structure. In this study, the scales being considered are the microscale at the directly impacted area, and the macroscale in the other area. In the different scale, complex phenomena, such as the interaction between transverse cracking and delamination, can be effectively described. The main damage mechanisms, i.e. fiber breakage, matrix microcracking and the debonding of adjacent layers, are described on the basis of 3D stress state using simple failure criterion of the constituent throughout the thickness. The interlaminar

interface is defined as a two-dimensional mechanical model which transfers traction forces and displacements from one ply to the next. Its mechanical behavior depends on the angle between the fibers of the two adjacent layers. In the case of delamination, this type of approach is often used introducing the interlaminar damage only.

In order to develop the multiscale model, direct numerical simulation(DNS) concepts are adopted. Especially the impact on composite materials or systems is a structural dynamics problem that leads to local damage phenomena. To analyze this local behavior of composite materials that are mixture of reinforcement (fiber) and bonding materials (matrix), it is desirable that we may need to look into the material responses inside the composites by separate discretization of fiber and matrix to see the interaction behavior between fiber and matrix, since impact damages highly depend on the local microscopic behavior of the composite materials as mixtures. We call this approach Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS)[3].

In this paper, we will show the basic aspects of multiscale modeling of composite plates on the basis of concepts of DNS. And the overall goal of the present study is to provide insight into the dynamic response of composite plates subjected to a transverse low-velocity impact loading by means of multiscale modeling. For this purpose, we will develop the parallel contact-impact finite element code which can be compatible with a hundreds of parallel computing nodes and a multi-scale models will be developed to predict impact behavior and failure mode.

TWO-SCALE MODELING OF COMPOSITE LAMINATE PLATE

In this work, the virtual specimen consists of the macro-scale parts and the micro-scale parts as shown in the figure 1 as multi-scale model for the impact analysis of composite plate. In macro-scale parts, the composite materials are considered as homogenized anisotropic materials and anisotropic constitutive equations are directly adopted. The lamina's mechanical properties could be obtained by smearing the constituents' (fiber and matrix) mechanical properties into an assumed homogeneous laminate to attain idealized uniform strength and stiffness throughout the structure. In micro-scale model, composite materials are regarded as mixture of different isotropic materials and separate discretization of fiber and matrix is required to describe the micro behavior of the constituents.[4]

However, impact damage, as any physical phenomena, exists in general on different scales and appears differently depending on the scale of observation. The microscopic behavior is determined by interactions between particles and influences macroscopic properties of the considered system. However, the connection between microscopic and macroscopic is often difficult to establish.

Here, we use the DNS concepts in microscopic modeling and implementation of interface between micro model and macro-scale model is made by tied interface constraints which is provided by LS-DYNA[5]

(b)
 Fig. 1 (a) Micro-scale modeling, (b) Boron Fiber and Epoxy matrix assembly

Fig. 2 Macro-scale modeling, Boron/Epoxy assembly

Micro-Macro model implementation-Tied Interface

Implementation of tied interface constraints are exploited in order to connect macro-scale model with micro-scale model. Sudden transition in zoning are permitted with the tied interfaces. First, we distribute the nodal forces and nodal mass of each slave node to the master nodes which define the segment containing the contact point, i.e., the increments in mass and forces

$$\Delta f_m^i = \phi_i(\xi_c, \eta_c) f_s$$

are added to the mass and force vector of the master surface. After the summation over all slave nodes is complete we can compute the acceleration of the master surface. The acceleration of each slave node a_{i_s} is then interpolated from the master segment containing its contact points:

$$a_{i_s} = \sum_{j=1}^4 \phi_j(\xi_c, \eta_c) a_i^j$$

Velocities and displacements are now updated normally.

For verify the use of tied interface constraints, stress reflections at the tied interface are observed through simple dynamic problem, bar impact problem. Some reflected stress waves may effect a change in global stress wave propagation and dynamic behavior, so that observation of the stress history at the tied interface is needed. These tests include:

- (a) isotropic material and no tied interface
- (b) isotropic material and tied interface
- (c) orthotropic material, complex geometry and tied interface (3D orthogonal woven composite bar)

(a) isotropic & no tied case (b) isotropic & tied case (c) orthotropic & tied case

(d) stress wave propagation at a element in the bar (e) stress history at the two face to face elements in contact with tied interface

Fig. 3 Verification of the use of tied interface in the multi-scale model

From these calculations, Fig. 3 (d) shows the stress wave propagation comparison between tied and no tied cases which have isotropic materials, and the difference of the two cases is quite small and we could conclude that the effect of tied interface is quite small. And Fig. 3 (e) shows the stress history at the two face to face elements in contact with tied interface on the 3D orthogonal woven composite bar which has the relatively geometrical complexity. From this result, the peak values of stress wave at the adjacent elements to the tied interface as boundary area appear at the same time, and the phase of stress wave is preserved. Therefore, use of tied interface constraint is verified on the multiscale modeling we developed.

VIRTUAL EXPERIMENT

The response of composite plates under low-velocity impact loading is obtained by using the dynamic explicit finite-element code, LS-DYNA3D[4] for virtual experiment on the supercomputer. LS-DYNA3D is a general-purpose, explicit finite element program used to analyze the nonlinear dynamic response of three-dimensional structures such as simulation of contact/impact problem, explosive forming, automobile crashworthiness etc.

The composite plates studied here are boron/5505 epoxy laminates [0₂/90₆/0₂]. It has 0.5 volume fraction and boron fiber and 5505 epoxy matrix have the characteristics in the following table 1, 2. The plate is modeled by square array of a lot of numbers of cells considering DNS concepts as Fig.1. The interlayer bond is assumed perfect with no debonding or slipping between layers during impact. Fig. 4 shows the problem configuration and the mesh of the specimen (200mm × 200mm × 1.80mm, 10 plies) that has 2,191,500 brick elements (8 node) and 6,574,500 degrees of freedom. The impact is applied at the center of the plate by the impactor, which has a shape of sphere with 20 mm radius and 27J impact energy (mass = 2.3kg, the initial velocity = 5m/s). The impactor is assumed to be rigid and consists of 110 shell elements. This study is performed using 8 node IBM SP2 parallel computer systems in Seoul National University.

Fig. 4 Problem configuration (impactor, virtual specimen(plate), finite element mesh of plate

Material	E (GPa)	ν	Density (g/cm^3)
Boron	441	0.1	2.57
5505 Epoxy	7.24	0.35	1.20

Table 1. Material Properties of fiber and matrix (micro model)

Boron/Epoxy	E_L (GPa)	E_T (GPa)	G_{LT} (GPa)	ν_{LT}	ν_{TL}	Density (g/cm^3)
Properties	207	19	4.8	0.21	0.0019	2.007

Table 2. Material Properties of Boron/Epoxy (macro model)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Virtual impact experiments are carried out on the virtual specimen, Boron/Epoxy cross-ply composite plate[0₂/90₆/0₂]. The effective stress value(von Mises Stress) at each constituent and ply can be obtained directly without any specific assumptions and impact load transfer mechanism through thickness of a specimen also could be observed. From Fig. 5~6, it is noticed that the distribution of

von Mises stress has a peanut shape and these results correspond with the experiment result. [6] And the existence and location of failure area of this specimen can be also predicted using these results. Fig. 7 show the impact load transfer mechanism through thickness of the specimen. In these results, the contribution of fiber and matrix to sustain the impact loading could be found graphically with time.

Fig. 5 Calculated effective stress(von Mises) distribution and experimental result

Fig. 6 Section view and von mises stress distribution

Fig. 7 Stress Distribution through thickness with time

CONCLUSION

The aim of this paper is to propose a method to simulate impact behavior in local impacted area with the help of Direct Numerical Simulation of laminated composite plates. By the use of IBM SP Nighthawk II parallel computer systems and LS-DYNA3D code, this method provides ability of analyzing the stress distribution of each fiber and matrix during impact time in local area. Using these DNS concept and the development of multi-scale modeling, the deflection and stress distribution of boron-epoxy laminated composite plates subject to impact of rigid ball have been investigated and presented graphically. It is hoped that a constituent-based failure criterion considering three dimensional stress components can be developed and progressive failure prediction considering post-impact residual strength will be obtained.

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